

Assessment of Awareness and Efficacy on Antenatal Care Service Delivery among Pregnant Women in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigates assessment of awareness and efficacy on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West, Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprise all pregnant women in North-West, Nigeria within the period January-March, 2023. The sample sizes for this study consist of 768 pregnant women selected from three sampled states in North-west zone, Nigeria using multi-stage sampling technique. A close-ended questionnaire title 'Antenatal Care Awareness and Efficacy Questionnaire (ACAEQ)' was used to obtain responses from the respondents. The questionnaire consists of three (3) sections. The instrument was validated by five (5) professionals in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria. Cronbach Alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument; the reliability was 0.859. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions. Two hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using independent sample t-test. Findings from the study revealed that pregnant women in North West Nigeria lacks adequate awareness of antenatal care service delivery. Efficacy of antenatal care service delivery in North-West Nigeria is poor. Based on findings of this study, it was concluded that Pregnant women in North West Nigeria lacks adequate awareness of antenatal care service delivery. It was, therefore recommended that adequate awareness of antenatal care service deliver should be provided through adequate sensitization program.

Keywords: Awareness, Efficacy, Antenatal care, and Pregnant women.

Introduction

Antenatal care is a medical and general care that is provided to pregnant women during pregnancy and it is goal-oriented provided with the aim of meeting both psychological and medical needs of pregnant women within the context of health care delivery system. Furthermore, antenatal care has been found to be effective in the treatment of anemia, hypertension and sexually transmitted diseases (World Health Organization (WHO), 2020). Additionally, antenatal care may take place in hospital, healthcare centers or clinics by health professionals, and its aim is to ensure that the mother reaches the end of pregnancy as healthy as, or even healthier than she was before the pregnancy (Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH), 2021). It highlights the care of antenatal to pregnant mothers as an important element in maternal healthcare as appropriate care will lead to successful pregnancy outcome and healthy babies (Sharma, 2020). All pregnant mothers are recommended to go for their first antenatal check-up in the first trimester to identify and manage any medical complication as well as to screen them for any risk factors that may affect the progress and outcome of their pregnancy (WHO, 2021).

Pregnancy and child birth is a natural process which in most cases comes to good end even without any intervention; however, in a relatively high proportion of pregnancies there are complications and some of which are very serious and of a life-threatening nature (Igbokwe, 2021). Some of these complications may be anticipated, because of some unavoidable risk factors (Ochola, 2019). Complications associated with various maternal issues are indeed major contributors to reproductive

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health concerns among millions of women worldwide. Most of the women between 15-49 years of age are not aware of health care services; therefore, this group is highly vulnerable to pregnancy-related problems. Death and illness from pregnancy-related causes are highest among poor women everywhere in societies who are disproportionately poor, illiterate and politically powerless (Ocholla & Ayayo, 2021). The risk of dying as a result of pregnancy or child birth during a woman's life time is about one in six in the poorest part of the world Nigeria inclusive, compared with about one in 30,000 in Northern Europe. Such a discrepancy possesses a huge challenge to meeting the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to reduce maternal mortality by 75% between 2015 to 2025. Some developed countries have managed to reduce their maternal mortality while most of the developing countries lag behind in which further progress is jeopardized by weak health system (WHO, 2021).

Nigeria is Africa's most populous country with a population of over 140 million people (National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), 2017). It is reported that, there are about 31 million women of childbearing age (Abimbola, Okoli, Olubajo, Abdullahi & Pate, 2020). Maternal mortality is estimated to be more than twice as high in the rural areas (828 deaths per 100,000 live births) than in the urban areas (351 deaths per 100,000 live births) (Abimbola et al., 2017). Zonal variations abound in maternal mortality figures across Nigeria. WHO (2020), reports that Maternal Mortality Rates (MMR) are significantly higher in Northern Nigeria compared to the Southern part of the country. The North West zones with MMR of 1,549 deaths per 100,000 live births and 1,025 deaths per 100,000 live births with a rates of about ten and six times higher than that in the South West (165 deaths per 100,000 live-births) (Adegoke, et al., 2020). High MMRs in the Northern part of the country significantly impacts on the national MMR, estimated at 545 deaths per 100,000 livebirths (National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), 2021). These figures indicate the need for high impact interventions to reduce maternal mortality, while paying particular attention to rural communities in Northern Nigerian.

The Health Belief Model (HBM) originated from psychosocial theory, designed by Lewin, which is based on a phenomenological orientation to positive and negative influences in the individual's subjective world as they affect behaviour. The model is a value expectancy model that examines an individual's behaviour, values, and judgment of how an action will provide a positive outcome. HBM examines the effects of health beliefs and decisions methods in making behavioural changes. This model is appropriate for this study because it examines the psycho-social factors associated with compliance to ANC service among mothers of under-five children. The effects of these factors are influenced by the benefits and efficacy of preventive action and perceived barriers to preventive activities. HBM focuses on the efficacy and beliefs of individuals. The HBM is based on individual participation in health-related action if that individual: (1) feels that a negative health condition can be avoided; (2) has a positive expectation that she will avoid a negative health condition by participation in prevention strategies measures; and (3) believes that she can successfully participate in the health-related action.

According to Harrison (2019), pregnant women with greater awareness of ANC, have greater likelihood of better pregnancy and delivery outcomes. This is likely because acquiring awareness of ANC equips pregnant women to make appropriate decisions about their health including during pregnancy and childbirth. A better informed woman on ANC is more likely to make appropriate decisions during obstetric emergencies (Jammeh, Sundby & Vangen, 2020), but many developing countries have women with poor awareness of ANC which is more prevalent in rural communities (Sharma, 2020). In addition, Mushi, Mpembeni and Jahn, (2022), mentioned that awareness about ANC services could help reduce pregnancy-related health risks and promote safer pregnancies and deliveries. Ocholla et al (2021), reported that the probability of a woman of reproductive age having more awareness of ANC services should increase with age, number of deliveries as well as number of antenatal care (ANC) visits by the woman.

Igbokwe (2021), indicated that the antenatal care efficacy among pregnant women is still low due to many factors that need to be examined such as socio demographic factors, awareness of social support. Igbokwe (2021), conclude that eliminating such factors is important to increase the women's participation in Antenatal Care. Gazali, Muktar and Mahamoud's (2022), reported that socio-cultural factors influence efficacy of ANC services. These factors are associated with the socio-cultural beliefs and efficacy, tradition, norms and values of people that influence the way and manner in which they seek medical help. Marchie (2021) carried out a study in Edo South senatorial district, and found out those socio-cultural variables (female genital mutilation, early marriage/child bearing, traditional obstetric care services) influence ANC services efficacy.

North-West zone, is known for poor health care system, inadequate maternal and child health care, illiteracy and poor socio economic status (NDHS, 2021). United State Agency for International Development (USAID) (2022), reported that North West zone of Nigeria like other geo-political zones in Nigeria has formulated strategies such as primary health care program, which, however, faces tremendous challenges in achieving national wide coverage on maternal and child birth care. In North West zone, hospital records indicated that 70% of maternal deaths are directly attributable to complications of pregnancy, labor & delivery, while 30% are from infections occurring during pregnancy. About 90% of the maternal deaths are considered

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preventable provided that community knowledge is sufficiently raised and basic health services are made accessible. Maternal mortality rates are reportedly 2.7 times higher in women who had not received ANC. The situation is much worse in rural areas of the North-West zone where maternal mortality rates are found to be two or three times higher due to unavailability of ANC and obstetrics management for high risk pregnancy (John, 2022). The foregoing mind troubling issues prompted the researchers to undertake research study on the assessment of awareness and efficacy on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to assess:

1. Awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria
2. Efficacy of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of Awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?
2. How adequate is the Efficacy of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in level of awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?
2. There is no significant difference inefficacy of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The sample sizes for this study consist of 768 pregnant women selected from three sampled states in North-west zone, Nigeria using multi-stage sampling technique. The research instrument used for this study was a closed ended questionnaire title ‘Antenatal Care Awareness and Efficacy Questionnaire (ACAEQ)’ was used to obtain responses from the respondents. The questionnaire consists of three (3) sections. Section A contained three (3) statements on personal data of the respondents. To score the responses of the respondents, as based on how they felt towards a particular item, the 4-point scale was used as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) =4; Agree (A) =3; Disagree (DA) =2; Strongly Disagree (SD) =1. Therefore, any mean score of response that is 2.5 and above were considered acceptable or positive and any mean score of response that is below 2.5 was not acceptable but regarded as negative. In order to determine the face and content validity of the research instrument, the draft copy of the structured questionnaire were submitted to five (5) professionals in the Departments of Human Kinetic and Health Education, Nursing Science and Educational Psychology. To ascertain the reliability and internal consistency of the instrument used for the study, simple random sampling was used to select twenty (20) questionnaires were administered to 20 pregnant women who attended two health facilities on Tuesday and Thursday at Samaru Primary Healthcare centre and Samaru clinic respectively in Kaduna State. Hence, a total of 40 questionnaires were administered to 40 respondents. The instrument was reliable with 0.804 using Cronbach Alpha test

Mean and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions, while, independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses. at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of Awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?

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Table 1: Mean Scores of Responses on awareness of ANC Services among Pregnant women in North-West Nigeria

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	I am aware of HIV screening during ANC clinic in the hospitals	2.25	1.06	Unaccepted
2	I have good understanding of the benefits of weight measuring	2.05	1.07	Unaccepted
3	I am aware of regular checking of blood pressure during ANC	2.52	1.43	Accepted
4	I am aware of respiratory rate measurement for the Pregnant mothers	2.59	1.22	Accepted
5	I am aware of hepatitis B virus screening during ANC clinics	2.37	1.23	Unaccepted
6	I am aware of immunization with tetanus toxoid vaccine	2.56	1.21	Accepted
7	I have good understanding of blood sugar level test during ANC	2.28	1.19	Unaccepted
8	I am informed about blood screening for malaria during ANC visit	2.46	1.17	Unaccepted
9	I am aware of ultrasound scanning during ANC visit	2.31	1.12	Unaccepted
10	I am aware of urine test for protein and blood glucose during ANC	2.12	1.10	Unaccepted
Aggregate Mean		2.35	1.16	

(Field Survey, 2023).

Observation of Table 1 shows that the respondents revealed that they are not aware about antenatal care services as most of the mean scores of responses were less than 2.50, except items 3, 4, and 6 where the means score of responses were 2.50 and slightly above. Know about checking of blood pressure (2.52), respiratory rate measurement (2.59), and immunization with tetanus toxic vaccine (2.56). The aggregate mean score of 2.35 indicates that pregnant women in North West Nigeria lack adequate awareness of antenatal care service delivery.

Research Question Two:

How adequate is the Efficacy of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Responses on efficacy of ANC Services among Pregnant women in North West Nigeria

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	I do go for HIV screening during ANC clinic in the hospital	2.60	1.01	Accepted
2	Weight measurement is a normal practice for me during ANC	2.72	0.92	Accepted
3	Regular checking for blood pressure is done on me during ANC	2.79	0.92	Accepted
4	I always seek for nutritional advice during antenatal clinic	2.44	1.17	Accepted
5	I always go to the clinic for urine examination during ANC visit	2.30	1.21	Unaccepted
6	Health education talk on personal hygiene is deliver	2.13	1.16	Unaccepted
7	I attend ANC appointment days regularly	2.45	1.98	Unaccepted
8	I attend screening for hepatitis B during ANC visits	2.25	1.15	Unaccepted
9	I always take care of my personal hygiene during pregnancy	2.44	1.17	Unaccepted
10	I go for respiratory rate checking whenever I visit ANC clinic	2.43	1.17	Unaccepted
Aggregate Mean		2.46	1.19	

(Field Survey, 2023).

Table 2 shows that the respondents did not really practice these ANC services as revealed by the mean scores and standard deviation, except services such as HIV screening (2.60), weight measurement (2.72); and regular checking of blood pressure (2.79) respectively. The aggregate mean score of 2.46 indicates that pregnant women in North West Nigeria had no efficacy of antenatal care service delivery.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in level of awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?

Table 3: One sample t-test Analysis on Awareness of ANC Services among Pregnant women in North-West Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-value	P-value.
Awareness	2.351	1.157	9	40.553	0.12

t (9)=1.833 P< 0.05 Significant.

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The result shows the t-value of 40.553 at 9 degree of freedom (df) and a significance level of 0.12 at 0.05 level of confidence. This result supports the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in level of awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria. The hypothesis was therefore retained. Thus, pregnant women in North West Nigeria lack adequate awareness of antenatal care service delivery

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference inefficacy of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria?

Table 5: One sample t-test Analysis on efficacy of ANC Services among Pregnant women in North-West Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-value	P-value.
Efficacy	2.45500	1.096	9	37.969	0.10

t (9)=1.833 P< 0.05 Significant.

A careful look at the result from the null hypothesis tested shows that the observed t-value of 37.969 at 9 degree of freedom (df) and a significance of 0.10 at p< 0.05. With this observation of the results presented in the Table 4.12 the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference inefficacy of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North West Nigeria was accepted. Thus, the results showed that the efficacy of antenatal care service delivery in North-West Nigeria is poor

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that pregnant women in North West Nigeria lack adequate awareness of antenatal care service delivery. This finding is in consonance with Gurmesa (2020), who reported that Pregnant women are not aware of antenatal care services, it could be in realization that awareness of Pregnant women is a major factor in determining the extent to which antenatal care services are used. Ibrahim (2021), identified factors associated with late antenatal care attendance in selected rural and urban communities in Kebbi state and found that inadequate knowledge about antenatal care services resulted into 2.2 times high odds for late antenatal care attendance than women who had adequate awareness in urban cities. The perception of no benefits derived from commencement of antenatal care early was associated with four times likelihood of late attendance in the urban city (WHO, 2021). Furthermore, with respect to awareness of ANC services, Andualalem, Hamel, Hana and Hale (2022), opined that 11.8% of the respondents did not know about antenatal care, the result was lower with El-Sherbini (2020) in Assiut General Hospital which was 25.5%. But their result was comparable with the result of Ibrahim (2021), 14.5% have no knowledge of antenatal care services among Pregnant women in Nigeria and 6+73% of Pregnant women in Zulmi general hospital lacked basic and essential awareness about antenatal care. Ekechi, Mustpha, Ibrahim and Bensen (2021), stated that out of 90% respondents, 80% of respondents displayed lack of adequate awareness of the benefits of health facility delivery with a skilled birth attendant.

The findings of this study showed that the efficacy of antenatal care service delivery in North-West Nigeria is poor. This finding is in line with Andualalem et, al; (2022), who found that from among respondents who had ever been pregnant only 47.9% of women followed antenatal care service. This finding was also in line with Ethiopia Demographic Health Survey (2020), which indicated that percentages of women who had antenatal care follow up at least one time were 28% and 34% respectively. Swedo (2021), revealed that lack of prenatal care is an important risk factor for maternal mortality, in urban India women with high levels of prenatal care were nearly four times more likely to seek care antenatal care from trained assistants at delivery than women with low levels of prenatal care, providing a potential explanation for the importance of prenatal care in maternal pregnancy outcomes. Sadly, the author noted, many women learn about the importance of prenatal care through loss and personal tragedy.

Conclusion

Pregnant women in North West Nigeria lack adequate awareness of antenatal care service delivery. Efficacy of antenatal care service delivery in North-West Nigeria is poor

Recommendations

1. Adequate awareness of antenatal care service deliver should be provided through adequate sensitization program
2. Efficacy of antenatal care service delivery should be provided by government and health personnel.

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